

STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF AGRICULTURAL MARKETS IN THE REGION

Isirailov A.A.

postgraduate student of correspondence course
Osh State University 331, Lenin Str, Kyrgyzstan

Dzhaparova E.S.

Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9129-7839>,
elmiradzh@mail.ru

***Abstract.** The article examines how various forms of domestic support and trade measures are related to how multilateral agricultural trade rules affect policy decisions. Trade can be a means of moving food to areas experiencing food shortages, an important mechanism for coping with falling production. In the long term, trade can provide an effective adjustment in the approaches to agricultural production in different countries. As the comparative advantage and competitiveness of agriculture varies across regions and countries, some countries are disadvantaged while others are gaining.*

Access to the EurAsEC market for Kyrgyzstan has a decisive significance due to its large size, geographical proximity and opportunities for transboundary infrastructure. As a result of the growth of trade, conditioned by exports, the removal of barriers to trade reduces the cost of strategically important imports, including fuel, gas, grain, metals, wood, chemicals and other products of Kyrgyz

products and other products. Trade policy allows for the establishment of international markets where countries can purchase products to ensure food security.

For Kyrgyzstan, access to the EurAsEC market is critical due to its large size, geographic proximity, and cross-border infrastructure capabilities inherited from the Soviet Union. In addition to promoting export-led growth, the removal of barriers to trade lowers the cost of strategically important imports, including fuels, gas, grains, metals, timber, chemicals and other products critical to Kyrgyzstan's industry. Membership in the composition entails support from the EAEU organizations and regional partners.

The government should create favorable conditions for domestic producers to increase the production and export of horticultural products, remove obstacles to their development. It is necessary to integrate small-scale regional fruit producers into value chains, facilitate access to productive resources and knowledge in the production, storage and processing of fruits, promote private investment in refrigeration and post-harvest processing facilities, and invest in safety and quality control systems food and innovation.

Keywords: *Agricultural economics, sustainable development, market, safety, regulation, products.*

For socio-economic development we need a diverse range, high quality of food for every inhabitant of the country, which determines the level and quality of nutrition of the population, health and longevity of man. Each country has an adequate organizational and economic mechanism of food security. Food security as an organizational and economic system is able to materialize the potential of food security of the country.

It includes the organization of the supply network, the promotion of domestic and imported agricultural products, raw materials and food from producers to consumers, the economic relations of participants in this process. Full provision of consumer needs in full-fledged food products, physical and economic availability of food, its qualitative state presupposes sustainable and sufficient levels of production, agricultural production and agricultural production.

Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and of course Kyrgyzstan export their products to the EU market. Thanks to the GSP + status, Armenia and Kyrgyzstan have the largest advantage, but our republic is on the list of EU trading partners, occupying 139 positions among 215 countries. This is the highest position in Russia (4th place), Ukraine (27th place). Kazakhstan has 29 positions with a total export volume of 12,773 mln. euro, Uzbekistan - 124th place, Tajikistan - 135th place with the volume of exports 94 mln. euro.

Kyrgyzstan can supply an order of 6,000 types of goods in the EU with zero customs duties. In the nature of exports to the EU, the increase in goods was of a non-voluntary nature, while the GSP + in most of its parts is distributed to food products. In connection with the high demand for organic products in the EU market, their offer falls behind. According to the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FIBL, the growth rate of the European organic market is maintained at a level of more than 10% per year.

Importing goods in the form of raw materials, the EU processes their finished products. Thus, the share of vegetables (51%) in the structure of imports exceeds, and food products make up 29%. Supplies to EU livestock products are linked to high standards and requirements, including internal production, satisfying internal demand for sufficient quantity and changing the culture of consumption of the population.

Among other goods, demand for dried fruits, fruits, nuts and high-quality, ecologically clean honey. Kyrgyzstan also exports agricultural products of the following species: seeds, grains, cereals, technical crops, vegetables, orchards, potatoes, fruits, dried fruits, nuts, food products. From the EAEU, the European Union, China, Uzbekistan and other states in the Kyrgyz Republic in 2020 imported 228,534,751 tons of agricultural products - this is 50,157,751 tons more than in the first half of 2019 (178,377 tons). In 2021, the CIS countries have increased deliveries to Russia of potatoes, carrots and beets, which are part of the "borscht set. Among the exporters are Belarus (98.3 thousand tons), Azerbaijan (84.7 thousand tons), Armenia (28.9 thousand tons).

The volume of imports of carrots from Russia from the CIS countries grew by 14% to 78.9 thousand. tons for the analogous period of 2020 to 90.3 thousand. tons in 2021. Country exporters of carrots - Belarus (65.4 thousand tons), Kyrgyzstan (12.7 thousand tons), Kazakhstan (6.6 thousand tons). Small volumes of deliveries to the territory of Russia in Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan and Turkmenistan. In 2021, the unloading of this vegetable began in Moldova, where the import has already exceeded 1 thousand. tons.

By comparison, Belarus by 2020 increased exports of carrots to Russia by 9.6%, Kyrgyzstan - by 43.3%, Kazakhstan - by 19.1%, Uzbekistan - by 16.8%. Exports of beets from Russia grew by 17.1% to 14.8 thousand. tons in 2020 to 17.3 thousand. tons in 2021. The leading supplier of beets in the Russian market - Belarus, from which imported 12.5 thousand. tons of this vegetable (17.9% more than for the same period in 2020). Also beets are sent to the Russian Federation in Uzbekistan (2.4 thousand tons) and Kazakhstan (1.2 thousand tons).

The abolition of the administrative mechanism of price regulation and their liberalization in the first years of independence, caused a sharp jump in prices in

the republic for consumer goods and services. In connection with the lack of water, there is a question about the cultivation of culture, which requires a lot of water. In Kazakhstan there is water, which farmers could irrigate. Agricultural sector asks to cancel the licensing of the use of underground water.

When the volume of sugar beet is reduced, and we have only 2 sugar factories, the plant will not produce sugar beets. At this time, they provide 60% of the consumption in sugar, the rest is imported. In case of reduction of settlements, there will be no 60% coverage of consumption, and 50% or 40%. The work will be lost at the factory workers, ie. this is a whole chain.

This will lead to the fact that on the table of Kyrgyzstanis will be imported sugar in exchange for local, which is valued much more. Dress with problems with fuel and chemicals, in the first place water. In Kyrgyzstan, the consumption of meat and meat products is increasing annually, and according to the statistics on the status as of September 1, 2021, all business entities in Kyrgyzstan produced 256 thousand.

645.9 tons of meat for cattle and birds, which is the highest level in 2020. at 1.6%. The increase in meat production in the republic is due to the growth of agricultural livestock, in addition to pigs.

Table 1. Meat production in slaughter weight (thousand tons)

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Kyrgyz Republic	212,4	216,6	221,3	226,2	230,4
Osh	43,5	44,4	43,1	44,3	47,2

All regions of the republic produced more meat than the corresponding period of 2020. In 2019, the register of production facilities included 31 meat processing enterprises, in 2020 - 35 enterprises, and now the register of production facilities subject to state registration includes 39 meat processing enterprises.

According to the Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Regional Development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2015-2020, the number of cattle increased by 15%, amounting to 1 million 715.7 thousand heads.

In Kyrgyzstan, for the period 2015-2019, the average weight of one head of an animal sold for meat decreased: for cattle - by 5%, for small cattle - by 3%. The growth in the production of meat and milk is provided almost exclusively by the growth of the number of animals. The increase in meat production in the republic is due to the growth in the number of farm animals, except for pigs and poultry. All regions of the republic produced meat more than the same period in 2020, especially Chui and Osh.

In 2021, as shown by the National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, Kyrgyzstan increased the import of cattle by 7 times. During this period, animals were imported from 4 countries and the EU. Retail prices for meat increased by an average of 22% over the year.

The demand for meat and meat products in Kyrgyzstan is increasing annually and, as of September 1, 2021, all economic entities of Kyrgyzstan produced 256,645.9 tons of livestock and poultry meat, which is 1.6% more than in 2020.

Table 2. Production of basic livestock products (farms of all categories)

	Production, thousand tons			Per capita, kg, pieces	
	2020	2019	2020 в % к 2019	2020	2019
	Cattle and poultry for slaughter, in (carcass weight)				
EAEU	14014	13560	103,3	76	74
Armenia	108	107	100,4	36	36
Belarus	1285	1240	103,6	137	132
Kazakhstan	1169	1121	104,3	62	61
Kyrgyzstan	230	226	101,9	35	35
Russia	11222	10866	103,3	77	74
	Milk				
EAEU	48364	46915	103,1	263	255

Armenia	654	668	98,0	221	225
Belarus	7765	7394	105,0	828	785
Kazakhstan	6051	5865	103,2	323	317
Kyrgyzstan	1668	1628	102,5	253	252
Russia	32226	31360	102,8	220	214
Eggs, million pieces					
EAEU	54787	55185	99,3	298	300
Armenia	755	721	104,6	255	243
Belarus	3495	3514	99,5	373	373
Kazakhstan	5066	5531	91,6	270	299
Kyrgyzstan	562	561	100,1	85	87
Russia	44909	44858	100,1	307	306

Due to the growth of livestock of farm animals, there is an increase in meat production in the republic, except for pigs. In 2020, the production of livestock and poultry for slaughter in Kyrgyzstan increased by 1.9%, in slaughter weight in the EAEU amounted to 14 million tons, which is 3.3% more than in the previous year. in all EAEU member states, growth was observed: in Kazakhstan - by 4.3%, Belarus - by 3.6%, Russia - by 3.3%, Kyrgyzstan - by 1.9% and Armenia - by 0.4%.

Table 3. Wool production in physical weight (tonne)

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Kyrgyz Republic	12 382	12 619	12 798	12 942.6	13 110
Batken	680	690	690	696.6	700
Osh	2 260	2 275	2 287	2 298	2 307

Wool production in the republic, compared to November 2020, was reduced in Batken and Osh regions by 98.3% and 98.7%, respectively, due to a decrease in the number of sheep and goats in the areas of these regions. Milk production also increased by 3.1% compared to 2019, amounting to 48.4 million tons in all EAEU member states, except for Armenia. This increase in milk production in the

republic is due to an increase in the number of cows by 19.7 thousand heads and an average milk yield per cow by 3.2 kg.

The Ministry of Agriculture, Water Resources and Regional Development of the Kyrgyz Republic notes that in Kyrgyzstan, the provision of dairy products is 100%. 1 million 200 thousand tons of milk is produced annually, of which almost 71% is processed, domestic consumption is about 300 thousand tons, the rest is exported. Dairy products are exported to Kazakhstan and Russia.

Table 4. Milk production (thousand tons)

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Kyrgyz Republic	1 524.6 1	556.2 1	589.7 1	627.8 1	668
Osh	303.5	310.5	316.1	321.7	328.1

Thus, products worth \$24.1 million were delivered to Kazakhstan in 2020, which is more than 52 percent of the total export of these products. About 46 percent of dairy products worth \$21 million were delivered to Russia. Kyrgyzstan also supplied dairy products to Uzbekistan (for \$705,000) and Tajikistan (for \$217,000).

Dairy products are presented on the foreign market, such as butter (37 percent of the marketable volume), cheeses and cottage cheese (21 percent), condensed and dry milk and cream (17 percent), non-condensed milk and cream (13 percent), fermented milk products (about 11 percent). In Kyrgyzstan, 64 milk processing plants operate under modern conditions.

In 2021, prices for certain socially significant goods increased from 8.3% (milk and dairy products) to 90% (vegetable oil). Export supplies to the EAEU countries increased by 32.2% as a result of an increase in supplies of fabrics made of synthetic multifilament yarns by 26.7 times, fresh and frozen fish - by 2.2 times, bread and flour confectionery products - by 1.7 times, shoes - 1.5 times, parts and

accessories for cars and tractors - 1.5 times. In the Medium-Term Forecast of Socio-Economic Development of the Kyrgyz Republic for 2022-2024, published by the Ministry of Economy and Commerce, regions will develop in 2022, a favorable business environment has been created as part of the implementation of the Regional Policy Concept for the period 2018-2022.

In each region, programs of cluster economic development will be developed on the basis of specialization in partnership with business structures, sectoral government bodies, the functions and powers of state bodies and local governments will be delineated. The financial and economic foundations for the development of local self-government bodies will be strengthened and improved, a system of state territorial administration will be introduced, taking into account the transition from sectoral to regional management.

For the development of infrastructure, resources will be attracted for the full implementation of programs for the development of drinking water supply and sanitation systems for settlements, irrigation, projects for the reconstruction and repair of local roads, with an emphasis on border areas. As a result, the well-being of the population of the regions will improve through the creation and implementation of the following clusters (tourism, clothing, vegetable oil production, and others). The state will provide serious support in providing land to the state fund of farmland and the issuance of cheap loans.

In 2021, the provision of animal feed in the country did not meet the required level. With an annual harvest of 3 million 850 thousand tons of feed for livestock, the stock turned out to be 12% less than usual. Grain harvest in Kyrgyzstan decreased by 34 percent. Although there is no shortage of livestock products in the country, the situation with crop production is different.

The sown area did not decrease, but the yield decreased by a third. In Kyrgyzstan, the number of sown areas of sugar beet decreased by 41.6%, sunflower - by 29.9%. In 2020, the total sown area of agricultural crops in farms of all categories of the EAEU amounted to 109.9 million hectares (100.5% compared to 2019), an increase in the total sown area was noted in all EAEU member states, except for Armenia.

The largest share in the total sown area of the EAEU is occupied by crops of grain and leguminous crops - 61.0% (in 2019 - 59.7%). The area under grain and leguminous crops in the EAEU increased by 2.8% compared to 2019, including: in Belarus - by 3.3%, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan - by 3.1%, in Russia - by 2.7 % and in Armenia - by 0.4%. The EEC materials noted that for the main industrial crops: sugar beet and sunflower, there was a decrease in areas in the EAEU - by 18.6% and 1.1%, respectively, compared to 2019.

The most significant decrease in the sown area of sugar beet was observed in Kyrgyzstan by 41.6% and Russia by 19.1%, sunflower - in Kyrgyzstan by 29.9%. Potato and open field vegetable crops in the EAEU also decreased by 4.5% and 0.5%, respectively. In Kyrgyzstan, the number of sown areas of sugar beet decreased by 41.6%, sunflower - by 29.9%. In 2020, the total sown area of agricultural crops in farms of all categories of the EAEU amounted to 109.9 million hectares (100.5% compared to 2019), an increase in the total sown area was noted in all EAEU member states, except for Armenia.

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Potato and open field vegetable crops in the EAEU also decreased by 4.5% and 0.5%, respectively. Kyrgyzstan's annual demand for sugar is 100-110 thousand tons, while domestic sugar production covers 50-60% of the population's needs. To fully cover the needs of the population, sugar is imported from Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Kazakhstan and other countries.

Due to the growth in demand for alcohol, world sugar prices set a new four-year record and its value peaked against the backdrop of the energy crisis and its pressure on the market. Since sugar is an exchange commodity, the influence of world markets has also affected domestic prices in Kyrgyzstan. According to the EAEU sugar balance in the 2021/2022 season, according to the expected imports of raw sugar and white sugar, sugar imports to Kyrgyzstan are planned in the amount of 30 thousand tons from the EAEU countries.

As for global cereal stocks, FAO predicts they will decline from 820.5 million tons to 817.5 million tons by the end of the 2021/22 season. Wheat production in the current season is estimated at 776.7 million tons, with consumption of 779.1 million tons. There will be a decrease in world wheat reserves from 286.9 million tons to 284.3 million tons. For fodder crops in the world, the harvest also does not compensate for consumption - 1 billion 503 million tons, while the need is 1 billion 512 million tons. In 2020, Kyrgyzstan experienced a 20% decline in trade turnover. And if exports during the coronavirus pandemic decreased by only 1.1%, then imports fell by 26.2% or \$1.3 billion.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, imports in Kyrgyzstan fell 1.3 times. Before and during the peak of the pandemic, Kyrgyzstan's main export destinations remained virtually unchanged. Deliveries of some types of products and soap-washing goods have been reduced. And imports of vegetables and flour increased slightly. Also, imports of rice, sugar, fruits and vegetables are creeping up.

But the volume of supplies of flour, tea, wheat, as well as bakery products are falling, the export of fertilizers, tobacco and tobacco products, as well as fruits and nuts has decreased. FAO Representation figures show that 14% of food produced is wasted and 17% is wasted.

Along with other stressors such as pests and diseases, natural disasters, biodiversity loss and habitat destruction, and conflict are increasing the challenge we face in meeting the world's growing food needs while reducing the environmental and impact of our agri-food systems on climate. At the same time, prices for food products and non-alcoholic beverages increased by 7.4%, alcoholic beverages and tobacco products - by 9.8%, non-food products - by 6.4%, tariffs for services provided to the population - by 2.4%.

The prices for lemons rose the most during this period - by 47%, buckwheat - by 31.6%, edible vegetable oils - by 21.5%, granulated sugar - by 20.5%. Also, as in Kyrgyzstan, the increase in food prices was recorded higher than in the EAEU, in Belarus by 7.8% and in Kazakhstan by 7.5%. The largest increase in prices for non-food products was observed in Belarus by 8.5%, for paid services - in Belarus by 5.9% and in Kazakhstan by 5.1%. Work to stabilize prices for socially important products is carried out on an ongoing basis, with special attention being paid to the issues of ensuring the country's food security.

From the state budget, food reserves in the amount of 1.5 billion soms were created for the purchase of wheat, over 300 million soms - vegetable oil and

granulated sugar. It was decided to exempt the import of grain and flour from VAT for 1 year, to agree on duty-free imports of white sugar and sugar cane from third countries. From VAT until December 31, 2021, exempted from import of farm animals.

The export (export) of certain types of agricultural products (wheat, rice, wheat flour, vegetable oil, granulated sugar, chicken eggs) is prohibited. According to the negotiations with the Russian Federation, the volume of supplied motor gasoline will be increased without paying export duties. Currently, the supply of duty-free diesel fuel is carried out in sufficient volume. State bodies monitor the current situation in these areas. Currently, there is a gradual lifting of restrictions on products from Kyrgyzstan, introduced by some countries of the EAEU. Since January 2021, the Consolidated Post information system has been used at the points of registration of goods when accounting for goods imported into the territory of the Kyrgyz Republic from the EAEU countries.

The Tax Service of the Kyrgyz Republic notes that thanks to the work of the Consolidated Post system, importers importing goods from the EAEU member countries issue shipping invoices online, regardless of where they are located, and also receive certificates from the tax authority for the import of goods through personal account" on the STS website.

The Republic of Belarus announced its intention to cancel the 10% value added tax rate on the sale of crop, beekeeping, livestock and fish products produced on the territory of the republic from July 1, 2017. On October 27, 2016, Kazakhstan canceled phytosanitary control at the border. Moreover, the decision to cancel this time was really implemented in full. With regard to veterinary control, the problem has not yet been resolved. In this situation, small and medium-sized businesses suffered most of all, which lost the opportunity to earn money on the re-

export of Chinese products, but did not receive free access to the markets of the EAEU countries and could not reorient themselves in a timely manner.

It is obvious that the subsequent removal of restrictions on Kyrgyz products and the expansion of supplies to the EAEU market will have a decisive influence on the positive perception of Eurasian economic integration in Kyrgyzstan. The ability of the EAEU to contribute to the realization of the transit potential of Kyrgyzstan, the creation of a transport and logistics infrastructure, will allow the Republic to integrate into regional trade and international initiatives of China.

Kyrgyzstan also counts on the realization of its transit potential and interests within the framework of conjugation of the EAEU and the SREB. In particular, as part of the interface, it is planned to build a China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway, which will connect the north and south of Kyrgyzstan and open access for the supply of goods to the markets of Western Asia, with the help of the China-Kyrgyzstan railway it will be possible to transport over 12 million tons of cargo in year, which will bring to the country's budget 150-200 million dollars a year only at the first stage, and then the state can receive about 500 million dollars a year from transit. Kyrgyzstan, along with Armenia, has the highest share of agriculture in the country's GDP in the EAEU (13.8%). Increasing agricultural export opportunities will go a long way towards improving perceptions of Eurasian integration. Uzbek importers are looking for ways to cooperate with Kyrgyz exporters. Since September 2019, Kyrgyz farmers began to export potatoes, small and large cattle to the neighboring state. From 2016 to 2019, Uzbekistan tripled its exports to Kyrgyzstan - from 67 million to 200 million dollars. Exports of Kyrgyzstan to Uzbekistan, according to the National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, during this time increased by only 10% - from 125 million to

138 million dollars. According to Uzbek statistics, the difference is many times greater - exports to Kyrgyzstan reached \$645 million.

Kyrgyzstan supplies mainly manufactured goods to the neighboring republic. In recent years, it has been actively increasing the export of coal, oil products, cement, and glass. The largest share of Uzbek exports to Kyrgyzstan is agricultural products. Uzbekistan also supplies textile and clothing products, plastic products and fertilizers. According to the National Statistical Committee of Uzbekistan, in 2019, trade between the countries reached \$792 million. According to the statistics of Kyrgyzstan - only 340 million dollars. The dynamics of trade shows that it will reach \$1 billion only due to the growth of imports from Uzbekistan.

Export volumes of Kyrgyzstan are growing slowly, the process is not stable. Moreover, Uzbekistan is increasing its exports to Kyrgyzstan, despite the pandemic.

Trade between the countries is carried out by rail and road, which transported 1.5 million tons of goods in 2019. At the level of the country's governments, the expansion of road capacity at border checkpoints and the improvement of conditions for the transit of passengers, vehicles and goods are being considered. To increase trade, Uzbekistan uses its capabilities to the maximum. In 2020, Uzbekistan increased the import of apples by 8.5 times - up to 8876 tons, most of the supplies came from Kyrgyzstan, China and Iran. Exports decreased by 61.8% - from 49.9 thousand to 19 thousand. Uzbekistan has sharply increased the import of apples against the backdrop of a lean season - from 1042 to 8876 tons (from 360.9 thousand to 2.85 million dollars, respectively). Moreover, the main volumes of imports (62.8%) of fresh apples fell on Kyrgyzstan.

Deliveries from this country increased 45 times - from 121.6 tons (at 47 cents per kg) to 5574.9 tons (at 0.29 cents per kg) (see Table 6).

Table 6. Imports of apples to Uzbekistan

	2019		January-December 2020	
	Number of tons	Thousand US dollars	Number of tons	Thousand US dollars
Total	1,042,1	360,9	8,876,3	2,851,0
Kyrgyzstan	121,6	57,9	5,574,9	1,656,4
China	369,1	210,8	1,166,5	541,1
Iran	373,4	59,7	1, 036,2	289,7
Kazakhstan	5,0	2,0	329,1	137,0
Pakistan	130,5	28,1	553,4	106,8
Ukraine	-	-	55,5	44,7
Armenia	-	-	84,0	40,0
Russia			36,6	23,2
Turkey			40,0	12,0
Turkmenistan	42,6	2,6		

Now the EAEU countries are fully provided with grain, sugar, vegetable oil, pork and lamb. Things are worse with fruits and berries, where there is still a partial dependence on supplies from states that are not members of the Eurasian Economic Union. Export of fruits, its increase will accelerate economic growth in exporting countries, create jobs and increase income levels in rural areas. Smallholder farmers will be included in value chains, resulting in increased fruit production and employment compared to other agricultural sub-sectors.

Gardening requires at least twice as much labor as growing crops. One job in this industry gives three jobs in other industries, not counting the increase in employment among farmers. The growth in fruit exports brings significant benefits to small farmers, because they are the ones who produce this type of product.

They not only increase their income, but also get access to loans and consulting and educational services provided to them by exporting companies. Job creation in the horticulture sector can solve the problem of employment of

migrants returning to Kyrgyzstan from Russia. In addition, there are jobs for rural youth who enter the labor market every year. Apricots, cherries and plums have the highest export potential among fresh fruits grown in the Kyrgyz Republic. Their export potential is estimated at \$17.1 million per year. The volume of the Chinese market for imported fruits reaches \$5.8 billion. The export of fruit, the increase in its volume, significantly accelerates economic growth in the exporting countries, creates jobs and increases the level of income in rural areas.

Smallholder farmers are being included in value chains and employment is increasing compared to other agricultural sub-sectors. Compared to growing crops, gardening requires at least twice as much labor. Along with the increase in employment among farmers, one job in this industry gives three jobs in other industries. The export of fruit is beneficial to small farmers who produce this type of commodity. They have increased incomes, loans and consulting and educational services from exporting companies are available. Created jobs in the horticulture sector solve the problem of employment of migrants from Russia. Rural youth are employed, who annually enter the labor market.

The highest export potential among fresh fruits is apricots, cherries and plums, which are grown in the Kyrgyz Republic. Their export potential is estimated at \$17.1 million per year. The Chinese market for imported fruits reaches \$5.8 billion and opens up opportunities for Kyrgyz exporters to diversify the geography of their supplies. By 2030, there will be an increase in Chinese demand for imports of cherries, grapes, plums and apricots to \$1.8 billion.

Entering Chinese markets also allows Kyrgyz exporters to get higher prices for their products. Cherry exports to China bring Kyrgyzstan \$3.17 per kilogram, while selling to Russia and Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz exporters receive only \$1.49 and

\$0.71. Along with Chinese markets, modern retail chains in the Russian Federation allow Kyrgyz exporters to increase the value of horticultural exports.

Currently, Kyrgyzstan exports 88 percent of sweet cherries and 99 percent of fresh apricots and plums to Russia and Kazakhstan. China requires from exporting countries stable quality and supply of fresh fruit. In this regard, the supply of fruits from Kyrgyzstan to China remains at a minimum level. Entering the Chinese market requires modern quality control systems, compliance with Chinese standards, constant contact with partners in China, beautiful packaging and a recognizable brand. Russia requires stable supplies of high-quality products that meet stringent requirements for the quality and safety of products, their internal properties (such as shape, color and taste), packaging and labeling, and accompanying documentation.

However, small farmers in the field work in a fragmented manner. Many do not have access to finance and information and educational resources. Production volumes are limited and product quality is unstable. In addition, domestic product quality and safety control systems often do not meet the standards of China or Russian retail chains. To increase competitiveness in the Chinese and Russian retail markets, fresh fruit exporters from the Kyrgyz Republic must increase volumes, improve quality, expand the range and ensure the stability of export supplies.

The government should create favorable conditions for domestic producers to increase the production and export of horticultural products, remove obstacles to their development. It is necessary to integrate small-scale regional fruit producers into value chains, facilitate access to productive resources and knowledge in the production, storage and processing of fruits, promote private investment in

refrigeration and post-harvest processing facilities, and invest in safety and quality control systems food and innovation.

Non-compliance with standards and technical regulations is also a problem in relations within the EAEU. For example, Kazakhstan has adopted emergency sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures to temporarily restrict imports of potatoes and meat. In addition, Kyrgyzstan faces strong competition from Uzbek exports, which directly compete with Kyrgyz goods. The fundamental reform of the export regime in Uzbekistan has led to increased direct competition between the EAEU countries in the field of exports, for example, fruits, vegetables and textiles.

To take advantage of shared borders with other countries and growing demand for agricultural products in the EAEU and China, reform of sanitary and phytosanitary standards is needed. The growth in the consumption of imported food also indicates problems in the management of the industry and significant shortcomings in the ongoing agricultural policy of the state. A key consequence of EurAsEC membership in Kyrgyzstan is improved access to a large regional market. Market access should improve due to tariff reform and, above all, the removal of restrictions through participation in the organization.

EAEU partners, mainly Russia, have pledged to provide financial support to Kyrgyzstan, which is struggling to finance compliance measures and develop infrastructure on its own (although these were all necessary conditions for joining the EAEU). According to the Ministry of Agriculture of the Kyrgyz Republic, imports account for 70% of the trade turnover structure. In the marketable products of the Kyrgyz Republic, mainly glass and cotton are sold abroad. Over the past 20 years, Kyrgyzstan has experienced drought 4 times.

Drought was noted in 2008, 2012, 2014 and 2021. Because of it, the yield of wheat decreased by 10 centners per hectare, as well as in other positions. In this regard, the use of water-saving technologies is very important. Today it is possible to purchase sprinkling and drip irrigation systems under a leasing program at a rate of 4.5% per year. The government allocated 426 million soms for the leasing program. In 2021, Kyrgyzstan received 8.5 billion cubic meters of water from the mountains, the losses amounted to 2 billion cubic meters.

The dynamics of water consumption (water runoff) is on the rise. In 2021, the peak will be reached - almost 8.5 billion cubic meters of water are actually received from the mountains, these are water and plus artesian wells. Agriculture consumes 4 billion cubic meters, and losses amount to 2 billion cubic meters. To preserve the water potential, a careful attitude to glaciers is necessary. Glaciers, if they do not accumulate their water, every year our water consumption will fall. Accordingly, the lower zones, the valley zones - Chui, Fergana - will suffer from drought. To solve the problem, afforestation and the development of agroforestry are needed.

Non-compliance with standards and technical regulations is also a problem in relations within the EAEU. For example, Kazakhstan has adopted emergency sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures to temporarily restrict imports of potatoes and meat. Market access should improve due to tariff reform and, above all, the removal of restrictions through participation in the organization.

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